

VETERINARY SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF THE INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF THE DRUG "SUPERIUM PANACEA" ANTIPARASITIC TABLETS FOR CATS IN IN VIVO EXPERIMENTS

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Abstract

The article determines the in vivo insecticidal activity of the antiparasitic drug "Superium Panacea" for cats. It has been established that the drug "Superium Panacea" has a pronounced insecticidal effect on wingless ectoparasitic insects *Ctenocephalides felis* and acaricidal effect on sarcoptoid ticks *Otodectes cynotis*. The duration of the protective effect of the drug was at least 28 days. The drug "Superium Panacea" with a wide spectrum of insecticidal and acaricidal action when applied to cats and kittens orally (per os), individually, once, during morning feeding with a small amount of feed or forcibly, according to the manufacturer's recommended schemes, is well tolerated by animals of different breeds and ages, which were used in the study and can be used for the treatment and prevention of mixed parasitosis.

Keywords: cats, Superium Panacea, *Ctenocephalides felis*, *Otodectes cynotis*

Introduction

Many external and internal parasites are registered in cats [1, 2]. The most common insect ectoparasites are the cat flea (*Ctenocephalides felis*), the human flea (*Pulex irritans*), hair eaters (*Felicolas ubrostratus*) and lice (*Linognathus setosus*) [3-6].

The main types of ticks that are common in Europe and Ukraine and parasitize cats are *Otodectes cati*, *Notoedres cati*, *Demodex cati*, *Cheyletiella blakei* [7-9].

Despite the availability and continuous increase of drugs for the treatment and prevention of ecto- and endoparasites in pets over the past two decades, external and internal parasites are still considered to be widespread [10, 11].

Ctenocephalides felis is one of the most important ectoparasites of dogs and cats worldwide due to its geographical distribution, dual parasitological effects as an invasive agent and vector of diseases [12].

Otodectes cynotis mites are the most common cause of otitis externa in cats. It is believed that they account for up to 85% of all cases of ear diseases [13].

An increase in the number of trips with domestic animals, plus climate changes affect the existing epizootic situation of certain ecto- and endoparasites or contribute to their introduction into different regions [14, 15].

The production of new antiparasitic drugs is driven by consumer requirements and aims to present a wide range of effective drugs that provide a long-lasting effect against ecto- and endoparasites and with a convenient way of administration [16].

Antiparasitic drugs that act on endo- or ectoparasites represent the second largest segment of the global animal health market, accounting for 23% of the market

share. However, relatively few new antiparasitic agents have been brought to market in recent decades [17].

Most modern drugs against ecto- and endoparasites for companion animals can be used for prevention or treatment. Resistance problems are present in most parasitic diseases, creating a clear market need for new resistance-reducing antiparasitic drugs with new modes/mechanisms of action [18].

The purpose of the work: to determine the insecticidal and acaricidal activity of the antiparasitic drug "Superium Panacea" in in vivo experiments on cats.

Materials and methods. The study of the drug against the entomozoans *Ctenocephalides felis* and *Otodectes cynotis* was carried out on the basis of the Center for the Treatment of Animals and clinics of veterinary medicine in the city of Kharkiv. The object of the study were cats of various breeds aged from 5 months to 4 years, body weight from 1 to 8 kg, the animals were housed in enclosures. The experimental group of cats (n=5) with siphonapterosis and otodectosis infestation was treated with the drug "Superium Panacea" according to the manufacturer's recommendations (taking into account the live weight of the animal's body and, accordingly, the weight of the tablet).

"Superium Panacea" antiparasitic tablets for cats is a combined drug with a wide spectrum of action against ecto- and endoparasites, which includes lufenuron, nitenpyram, moxidectin, praziquantel.

During the experiment, on the first, 2nd, 3rd, 7th, 14th, 21st and 28th days, the animals were observed: the skin and hair were examined for the presence of live ectoparasite fleas, noting the general condition, behavior, appetite, body temperature.

The diagnosis of skin-eating ticks of the *Otodectes cynotis* species was made on the basis of clinical signs, acarological research methods - microscopy of scrapings taken from areas of ears affected by parasites [19, 20].

At the same time, the index of parasitological damage was established - the intensity of invasion before and after treatment, and the effectiveness of drugs was determined in accordance with the

guidelines of the European Medicines Agency and the World Association for the Promotion of Veterinary Parasitology [21, 22].

Research results. In the experimental group of cats, before the use of the veterinary drug in the form of tablets, the average intensity of infestation by fleas of the species *Ctenocephalides felis* was 62.4 ± 11.2 ectoparasite insects per 100 cm^2 (Table 1).

Table 1.

Evaluation of the insecticidal effectiveness of the drug "Superium Panacea" against *Ctenocephalides felis* in cats ($M \pm m, n=10$)

Intensity of infestation, individuals/ 100 cm^2 to processing	Effectiveness of the insecticidal action of the drug, day					
	1		2		3-7-14-21-28	
	%	Intensity of infestation, individuals/ 100 cm^2	%	Intensity of infestation, individuals/ 100 cm^2	%	Intensity of infestation, individuals/ 100 cm^2
$62,4 \pm 11,2$	63,3	$22,9 \pm 8,2$	100	0	100	0

On the first day of the experiment, the effectiveness of the drug "Superium Panacea" in the experimental group of animals was 63.3%, with an average intensity of infestation by fleas of the species *Ctenocephalides felis* of 22.9 ± 8.2 ectoparasite insects per 100 cm^2 .

On the second day of the experiment, the effectiveness of the drug "Superium Panacea" for siphonapterosis of cats in the experimental group of animals was 100%.

On the third day of the experiment, when examining the skin and hair of cats and parasitological laboratory research, flea-ectoparasites of the species *Ctenocephalides felis* were not detected in the animals of the experimental groups.

During the 7th, 14th, 21st, and 28th days of observation of the animals of the experimental groups, reinvasion by wingless flea insects of the species *Ctenocephalides felis* was not observed.

The results of the conducted studies indicate that the drug "Superium Panacea" has a pronounced insecticidal activity against siphonapterosis of cats in relation to fleas of the species *Ctenocephalides felis*.

The duration of the protective effect of the drug against flea ectoparasites in cats was at least 28 days.

The body temperature of cats that participated in the study for siphonapterosis (ctenocephalidosis) when using the drug in tablet form was within the physiological norm for this species of animals. The use of the drug in tablet form did not cause physiological changes (appetite, behavior, activity) in cats. During the period of the experiment, increased individual sensitivity (excessive salivation, lacrimation, signs of skin irritation) in cats to the active substance (lufenuron, nitenpyram, moxidectin, praziquantel) was not noted.

Skin lesions of the inner part of the auricles and the external auditory canal were recorded in cats with clinical signs of skin-eating mites of the species *Otodectes cynotis*. Itching, hyperemia, swelling, and the presence of dark brown scabs and crusts in the auricles were observed in places where the tick was localized. According to an acarological study in the experimental group of cats before the use of the drug in the form of a tablet, the average intensity of infestation by ticks of the species *Otodectes cynotis* was 23.8 ± 3.8 specimens per animal (Table 2).

Table 2

Evaluation of the acaricidal effectiveness of the drug "Superium Panacea" against *Otodectes cynotis* in cats ($M \pm m, n=10$)

Intensity of infestation, to processing (specimens per animal)	Effectiveness of acaricidal action of the drug, day					
	1		2		3-7-14-21-28	
	%	Intensity of infestation, (specimens per animal)	%	Intensity of infestation, (specimens per animal)	%	Intensity of infestation, (specimens per animal)
$23,8 \pm 3,8$	56,3	$10,4 \pm 2,2$	94,1	$1,4 \pm 0,2$	100	0

On the first day, the effectiveness of the drug "Superium Panacea" in the experimental group of cats was 56.3%, with an average intensity of infestation by ticks of the *Otodectes cynotis* species of 10.4 ± 2.2 specimens per animal.

On the second day of the experiment, the effectiveness of the drug "Superium Panacea" in the experimental group of animals was 94.1% with an average intensity of infestation by ticks of the

Otodectes cynotis species of 1.4 ± 0.2 specimens per animal.

On the third day of the experiment, during the examination of the inner surface of the auricle of cats and acarological laboratory research - microscopy of scrapings taken from the auricle, skin mites of the species *Otodectes cynotis* were not detected.

During acarological examinations of cats on the 7th, 14th, 21st and 28th days after the use of the drug,

no reinfestation by skin-eating ticks of the species *Otodectes cynotis* was detected.

The research results obtained by us indicate that the drug "Superium Panacea" has a pronounced acaricidal activity for sarcoptic mange in cats.

Conclusions.

1. The conducted studies established that the antiparasitic drug for cats "Superium Panacea" (100 mg of the drug contains active substances: lufenuron - 10.0 mg, nitenpyram - 3.0 mg, moxidectin - 0.3 mg, praziquantel - 5.0 mg) has a pronounced insecticidal effect against wingless ectoparasitic insects *Ctenocephalides felis* and acaricidal action against sarcoptoid ticks *Otodectes cynotis*.

2. The drug "Superium Panacea" antiparasitic tablets for cats with a wide spectrum of insecticidal and acaricidal action when applied to cats and kittens orally (per os), individually, once, during morning feeding with a small amount of food or forcibly, according to the recommended schemes of the manufacturer, which belongs to "INTER LEK" LLC, Kharkiv (Ukraine), is well tolerated by animals of different breeds and ages that participated in the study and can be used for treatment and prevention of mixed parasitosis.

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